

NOTES

Studies on Mixed Ligand Complexes of Chromium(III) with Salicylaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone, Oxine and Nitrogen, Oxygen or Sulphur Donor Ligands

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In continuation of our stereochemical studies on mixed ligand complexes¹⁻³, we now report the preparation and characterisation of some mixed ligand chromium(III) complexes containing salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (H_2stsc), oxine (Hox) and $L = \text{pyridine (py)}/\gamma\text{-picoline } (\gamma\text{-pic})/\text{isoquinoline (iq)}/\text{urea (u)}/\text{triphenylphosphine oxide (tppo) or thiourea (tu)}$.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade and used as such. Salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone was prepared as per known method⁴.

$[Cr(stsc)(ox)(H_2O)]$: Aqueous solution of chromium(III) nitrate and ethanolic solutions of salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone and oxine were mixed in 1:1:1 molar ratio. To it was added dropwise dilute solution of ammonia with stirring till the solution attained a pH ~ 8 . The mixture was digested in a water-bath for 30 min. The resulting solid complexes were filtered off, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure over fused $CaCl_2$.

$[Cr(stsc)(ox)L]$; where $L = \text{py, } \gamma\text{-pic, iq, u, tppo or tu}$. Method 1: $[Cr(stsc)(ox)H_2O]$ was

treated separately with $\text{py}/\gamma\text{-pic}/\text{iq}/\text{u}/\text{tppo}/\text{tu}$ in 1:1 molar ratio in ethanolic medium. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 2 h. The separated complexes were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Method 2: Aqueous solution of chromium(III) nitrate, and ethanolic solutions of salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone, oxine and $\text{py}/\gamma\text{-pic}/\text{iq}/\text{tppo}/\text{tu}$ or aqueous solution of urea were mixed in 1:1:1:1 molar ratio. pH of the solution was adjusted to ~ 8 by adding dilute ammonia solution. The mixture was digested on a water-bath for 30 min. The resulting solid complexes were filtered off, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Analytical data revealed that the compositions of the compounds prepared by either of the above two methods were the same.

The infrared spectra (KBr) of the complexes on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer in the range $4000-400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and electronic spectra (acetone) on a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer, magnetic moments at room temperature, molar conductance of $\sim 10^{-3}M$ solution (in acetone) and molecular weight (Rast's method using biphenyl as solvent) were determined for characterising the complexes. The relevant data are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The molecular weight data indicate the compounds to be monomeric. The low molar conductance values ($\approx 1.8\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$) indicate their non-electrolytic nature.

Deprotonation of phenolic OH and coordination through oxygen was indicated by the appearance of

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd..	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
			Cr	N	S
$[Cr(stsc)(ox)(H_2O)]$	Brown	230	12.52 (12.71)	13.65 (13.75)	7.45 (7.86)
$[Cr(stsc)(ox)(py)]$	Light yellow	230	11.00 (11.08)	14.50 (14.90)	6.78 (6.82)
$[Cr(stsc)(ox)(\gamma\text{-pic})]$	Yellowish green	230	10.68 (10.76)	14.00 (14.40)	6.58 (6.62)
$[Cr(stsc)(ox)(iq)]$	Light yellow	235	9.95 (10.01)	13.03 (13.40)	6.09 (6.16)
$[Cr(stsc)(ox)(tppo)]$	Yellow	220	7.69 (7.78)	8.35 (8.39)	4.70 (4.79)
$[Cr(stsc)(ox)(u)]$	Yellow	>250	11.45 (11.55)	18.50 (18.60)	7.05 (7.11)
$[Cr(stsc)(ox)(tu)]$	Pale yellow	240	11.00 (11.15)	17.94 (18.00)	13.50 (13.70)

ν_{C-O} at $\sim 1350\text{ cm}^{-1}$. A sharp band at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($C=N$) of the Schiff base indicated bonding through azomethine nitrogen. Thus keto $\rightleftharpoons$ thioenol tautomerism of the Schiff base in alkaline medium and subsequent coordination to the metal ion by deprotonation of SH group are evident by the absence of ν_{SH} bands in the region $2800-2650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes⁵. This is further supported by a new band appearing at 660 cm^{-1} ($C-S$)^{6,7}. An additional band due to $\nu_{C=N}$ (formed by thioenolisation of Schiff base) appearing at $\sim 1480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ confirms the thioenol coordination of the ligand. The above facts clearly indicate that the ligand salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone behaves as a binegative tridentate ($\bar{O}, N, S$) ligand. Charles *et al.*⁸ observed ν_{C-O} at 1120 cm^{-1} in several oxine complexes of metals, the position of band slightly varying with the metal. In the present work, the appearance of a strong band at $\sim 1120\text{ cm}^{-1}$ clearly indicates the presence of oxine group coordinating through nitrogen and oxygen atoms as uninegative bidentate ligand^{9,10}. The presence of coordinated water molecule in the aqua-complex $[Cr(stsc)(ox)(H_2O)]$ was indicated by the bands at 3400 and 830 cm^{-1} . However, these bands due to water molecule are absent and new bands are observed in the complexes containing monodentate ligands. One of the bands of $\nu_{C=C} + \nu_{C=N}$ at $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to pyridine, γ -picoline and isoquinoline was found to overlap with the band of salicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone whereas the other one was found at $\sim 1550\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This suggests the coordination of these ligands through nitrogen atom¹¹. A negative shift of $20-25\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in ν_{C-O} in the urea complex indicates that urea is coordinated through oxygen atom to the metal ion¹² ($\sim 1660\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in free ligand). The ν_{P-O} band observed at 1070 cm^{-1} for triphenylphosphine oxide indicates participation of its oxygen atom in coordination¹³ (1195 cm^{-1} in free ligand). A negative shift of $20-25\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in $\nu_{C=S}$ in the thio-urea complex indicates that thiourea is coordinated through sulphur atom to the metal ion¹⁴ (685 cm^{-1} in free ligand). The presence of $Cr-O$ and $Cr-N$ bonds was evident from the ν_{Cr-O} and ν_{Cr-N} bands appearing at ~ 410 and $\sim 470\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively.

The electronic spectra of the complexes exhibit two bands in the region $18500-19200$ and $23200-23400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. These can be assigned to ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ transitions, respectively, which are typical of octahedral coordination¹⁵. Room temperature (298 K) magnetic moment values around $3.79-3.85\text{ B.M.}$ for these complexes suggest their spin-free nature.

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Some Complexes of Copper with Thiosalicylic Acid

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THE reactions of thioglycolic acid with Cu^{II} were first studied by Bjerrum¹ who found that Cu^{II} catalyses the oxidation of thioglycolic acid and used it as a basis for the microdetermination of copper. A complex with 1 : 1 molar ratio is formed when $CuCl_2$ and mercaptoacetic acid react at 10° in ethanol. Earlier work on the Cu^{II} -thiosalicylic acid (TAS) system is only sparse and deals mostly with analytical aspects²⁻⁴.

Experimental

$CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ thiosalicylic acid (TSA), and all the other reagents were of AnalaR grade.